

Poeciliids as indicators of environmental status in Arroyo Moreno, Mexico

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Abstract

Arroyo Moreno is a protected natural area located in Veracruz, Mexico, however, it currently faces various environmental impacts, which is why it is necessary to evaluate its environmental status for its conservation and management., the records of poeciliids reported for this area were analyzed, due to their ecological relevance and their proven usefulness as bioindicators, they were classified according to their level of protection and threat, finding that all species are in some risk category., so it can be inferred that despite presenting environmental degradation, Arroyo Moreno still preserves functional characteristics that allow it to host threatened species, which reinforces its importance as a priority conservation site.

Key Words: Bioindicator; conservation; native species; ecosystems; ichthyofauna; sustainability.

Introduction

Aquatic ecosystems have been subjected to increasing anthropogenic pressure because of unplanned human activities and inadequate resource management (Romano, 2016). This trend is largely driven by the exponential growth of the human population over recent decades, which has negatively affected biodiversity and compromised the integrity of aquatic environments. Consequently, many freshwater ecosystems are experiencing ecological disturbance and degradation, particularly those located in or near urban areas. Urban-related activities, including wastewater discharge, channelization, water abstraction, and tourism, have significantly altered the structure and functioning of these ecosystems (Velasquez-Velasquez & Vega-Cendejas, 2004).

Given these pressures, monitoring and assessment of water resources have become essential for detecting environmental changes and evaluating ecosystem health, thereby providing critical information for their conservation and sustainable management (Menges & Gordon,

1996). This need is especially relevant in priority conservation areas, which are natural regions of high environmental value where key ecosystem attributes converge with socioeconomic and cultural factors that influence their management and long-term preservation (Chávez *et al.*, 2015).

Due to their ecological value, fragility, and vulnerability to anthropogenic disturbances, these areas require innovative and multidisciplinary approaches for their identification, assessment, and conservation. Therefore, evaluating the environmental condition of aquatic ecosystems is fundamental for effective conservation planning. Environmental condition refers to the proper functioning of ecosystem processes and the interactions among biological communities that support integrity, resilience, and the provision of ecosystem services (Lavelle & León, 2018). It is important to note that this concept differs from toxicological assessment, which focuses on evaluating the effects of specific pollutants on ecosystem integrity (Hernández-Luis *et al.*, 2025).

In this vein, biological indicators have become valuable tools for assessing the environmental condition of ecosystems. Among these, endemic and vulnerable fauna have been widely used, as their presence and persistence reflect the quality and conservation status of the ecosystem (Chávez *et al.*, 2015). In recent years, fish have been increasingly recognized as effective environmental indicators, and assessments are often based on species composition, abundance, population attributes, and community structure (Rombouts *et al.*, 2013).

Arroyo Moreno is a protected estuarine ecosystem that faces multiple anthropogenic pressures despite its conservation status. Therefore, identifying practical biological indicators capable of reflecting its environmental condition is essential to support management and conservation efforts. In this context, the present study proposes the use of poeciliid fish as indicators to infer the environmental condition of Arroyo Moreno.

Related work

Previous studies have demonstrated the usefulness of fish communities as indicators of environmental quality and ecosystem condition. The presence or absence of fish species has been shown to reflect ecological changes occurring within aquatic ecosystems (Chapman, 2002; Masson *et al.*, 2007; Torres-Bugarin *et al.*, 2007; Obando-Bulla *et al.*, 2013; Alves & Mayer, 2025). Consequently, fish assemblages have been widely employed in environmental assessments based on species occurrence and community composition (Rombouts *et al.*, 2013).

In recent years, particular attention has been given to threatened species because their conservation status can provide valuable information regarding ecosystem integrity. For example, threatened native species have been used in Ecuador to assess ecological condition and support environmental management decisions (Rosete *et al.*, 2019). Likewise, North American species of the genus *Gambusia* have been used to identify conservation-priority

areas across the Great Plains and Osage Plains regions of the United States based on their distribution and conservation status (Hoagstrom *et al.*, 2011).

Among freshwater fishes, poeciliids are particularly well suited for environmental assessments due to their ecological importance within aquatic food chains, ease of identification, broad geographic distribution: they are found in both fresh and brackish water, with a distribution that ranges from the northeastern United States to northern Argentina., and occurrence across multiple trophic levels. These characteristics are considered essential attributes of effective fish bioindicators (Gómez-Márquez *et al.*, 1999; De la Lanza *et al.*, 2011; Hernández *et al.*, 2024).

Furthermore, several studies have emphasized that even species classified as Least Concern should be considered in environmental assessments because of their ecological relationships with more threatened taxa, thereby contributing indirectly to broader conservation efforts (Catalá, 2011; Evans *et al.*, 2022).

In addition to native species, introduced and invasive fishes can also provide valuable information about ecosystem condition. Several non-native poeciliids have been used as indicators of environmental degradation based on their presence or absence within aquatic systems. A notable example is the guppy, *Poecilia reticulata*, a species widely recognized for its invasive potential and broad distribution. The occurrence of this species has been associated with disturbed and degraded aquatic environments, making its presence a useful indicator of anthropogenic impacts on freshwater ecosystems (Restrepo-Santamaría & Álvarez-León, 2013; Sáez-Gómez & Prenda, 2019).

Conversely, native and endemic poeciliids have been highlighted for their conservation value. One such example is the sailfin molly, *Poecilia velifera*, an endemic species inhabiting the cenotes of the Yucatán Peninsula in southern Mexico. Cenotes represent ecologically important freshwater ecosystems, and *P. velifera* has been proposed as a flagship species for their conservation due to its endemism, ecological importance, and potential to promote the protection of other species sharing the same habitat (Ceballos & Barrientos-Medina, 2024). Collectively, these studies support the potential use of fishes of the family Poeciliidae as indicators of ecosystem condition while highlighting their value in conservation planning and management.

Research methods

The study was conducted in the Arroyo Moreno Protected Natural Area (PNA), designated as a State Ecological Reserve and forming part of the Jamapa River watershed in Veracruz, Mexico. Located within the central coastal plain of Veracruz, it encompasses the municipalities of Medellín and Boca del Río. The area is characterized as an estuarine

ecosystem dominated by mangrove forests that receive freshwater inputs from the Jamapa River and saline water through tidal exchange with the Gulf of Mexico (García *et al.*, 2019; Salas-Monreal *et al.*, 2019). Despite its protected status, various human activities, including tourism, fishing, industrial operations, livestock farming, and logging, are carried out within the area, contributing to ecosystem degradation (GEV, 2002; López-Portillo *et al.*, 2009).

Fish were selected for analysis because the presence or absence of species in a given location reflects ecological changes occurring within the ecosystem (Chapman, 2002; Masson *et al.*, 2007; Torres-Bugarin *et al.*, 2007; Obando-Bulla *et al.*, 2013; Alves & Mayer, 2025). Consequently, fish communities have been increasingly validated as environmental indicators, particularly through analyses based on species composition and occurrence records (Rombouts *et al.*, 2013).

Records of poeciliid species reported for Arroyo Moreno were analyzed (García *et al.*, 2019; Chávez-López *et al.*, 2023). These species were selected because of their ecological importance in aquatic ecosystems, where they serve as prey for larger fish, contribute to insect population regulation, consume plant and animal detritus, and participate in decomposition processes and the recycling of organic resources, among other ecological functions (Hernández *et al.*, 2024). Furthermore, they meet the criteria established for the selection of fish taxa as environmental indicators, including ease of identification, ecological relevance and occurrence within the study area, and representation across different trophic levels (De la Lanza *et al.*, 2011). The conservation and protection status of the selected species was determined according to the Mexican Official Standard for species at risk (DOF, 2010), the conservation status assessment of North American freshwater fishes (Jelks *et al.*, 2008), and the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) Red List of Threatened Species (IUCN, 2025).

Results and discussion

In the Arroyo Moreno Protected Natural Area (PNA) six species of poeciliids have been recorded: five native and one exotic (Table 1).

Table 1. Poeciliid species recorded in the NPA “Arroyo Moreno”

Species	Distribution	NAFS	IUCN	ML
<i>Poecilia mexicana</i>	N		LC	
<i>Poecilia formosa</i>	N		LC	
<i>Gambusia sexradiata</i>	N		LC	
<i>Poecilia latipunctata</i>	N	E		Pr
<i>Belonesox belizanus</i>	N		LC	
<i>Poecilia reticulata</i>	E			

Distribution: N = Native, E = Exotic. North American Fish Status List (NAFS): E = Endangered, T = Threatened, V = Vulnerable, X = Extinct, Xp = Possibly Extinct. International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) Red List: LC = Least Concern, NT = Near Threatened, VU = Vulnerable, EN = Endangered, CR = Critically Endangered, EW = Extinct in the Wild, EX = Extinct. Mexican Legislation (ML): E = Probably Extinct in the Wild, P = Endangered, A = Threatened, Pr = Subject to Special Protection.

As reported, poeciliid species have great ecological importance in the habitats where they are found, reflecting the condition of those habitats, and have therefore been used as models of ecological and environmental processes (Stockwell & Henkanaththegedara, 2011). Among the analyzed species in this study, *Poeciliopsis latipunctata* stands out due to its conservation status, being classified as Endangered in the North American freshwater fish conservation assessment (Jelks *et al.*, 2008) and as a species under Special Protection under Mexican legislation (DOF, 2010). The remaining species are currently categorized as Least Concern. Nevertheless, because all analyzed fishes belong to the family Poeciliidae, they share similar ecological requirements (physical, chemical, and biological) and are therefore likely to exhibit comparable responses to environmental disturbances (Holt & Miller, 2011). Furthermore, previous studies have highlighted the importance of including Least Concern species in environmental assessments, as they are often ecologically linked to species facing higher extinction risks; consequently, their conservation may indirectly contribute to the protection of more threatened taxa and to the conservation of the ichthyofauna in general (Catalá, 2011; Evans *et al.*, 2022).

It is important to note that the occurrence of introduced fish species is frequently associated with ecosystem degradation. Such is the case of the guppy, *Poecilia reticulata*, an exotic poeciliid species that has been recorded in Arroyo Moreno. Although this species is widely used as a model organism in environmental sciences (McKellar & Hendry, 2022), it is also recognized for its high invasive potential, and its presence has been directly linked to

environmental deterioration and degradation in aquatic ecosystems (Restrepo-Santamaría & Álvarez-León, 2013; Sáez-Gómez & Prenda, 2019). Therefore, its occurrence in Arroyo Moreno may indicate a certain degree of ecological degradation.

The analysis of threatened species has proven to be an effective tool for supporting environmental management in other regions. For example, in the Manabí region of Ecuador, threatened native species were used to assess regional ecological condition (Rosete *et al.*, 2019). Similarly, in North America, fishes of the genus *Gambusia* have been used to identify areas of conservation priority based on their distribution and conservation status (Hoagstrom *et al.*, 2011). As a more direct precedent, the sailfin molly, *Poecilia velifera*, has been proposed as a flagship species for the conservation of cenotes in Yucatán, although not specifically as an environmental indicator (Ceballos & Barrientos-Medina, 2024).

The findings of this study provide a valuable tool for inferring environmental condition and supporting decision-making in the management and conservation of this protected natural area. On one hand, the presence of an exotic species suggests some degree of environmental degradation. On the other hand, the composition of the poeciliid community includes species of considerable conservation importance due to their protected status. This indicates that, despite the anthropogenic pressures affecting Arroyo Moreno, the ecosystem remains in a relatively favorable ecological condition. The persistence of threatened poeciliid species suggests that the ecosystem still retains key functional characteristics necessary to support these species and other aquatic organisms. Consequently, Arroyo Moreno should be considered a priority area for conservation, in agreement with previous studies that have identified mangrove ecosystems as areas of high conservation priority (Franco & Barrientos-Medina, 2017).

Conclusion

The poeciliid species of Arroyo Moreno proved to be a useful indicator of the environmental status of this protected natural area. While the presence of *P. reticulata* suggests environmental degradation, the persistence of native species of great ecological importance, including one listed as endangered and subject to special protection (*P. latipunctata*), indicates that the ecosystem still maintains important ecological functions. These findings highlight the conservation value of Arroyo Moreno and support its continued protection and monitoring as a priority area for biodiversity conservation.

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